

A VIRTUAL GREENTECH LABORATORY

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It is crucial for the development of tomorrows green technologies, to ensure a sufficient engineering work force in the future. However, application for engineering educations is low. Here I present an innovative virtual greentech laboratory that aims to educate and inspire young people to study greentech engineering. Furthermore, the project aims to directly reduce the use of chemicals and lab-equipment through replacement of some experiments with *in silico* simulations. In the virtual laboratory genetic engineering can be applied to develop novel enzymes for green biofuel production and washing at lower temperatures, to produce engineered bacteria that can detect and degrade heavy metals, to produce medicine and more. The procedures that can be applied are technically correct, and it is possible to use techniques such as 1) gene design and synthesis, 2) genetic engineering of bacteria and yeast, 3) fermentation of genetically engineered cells to produce e.g. enzymes and 4) testing of the produced protein and calculations of the resulting impact on the environment. The virtual laboratory is designed to give users an experience of being in a real lab through stylish 3D animations and interaction, and is expected to be extremely efficient for both e-learning and inspiration of young people, as well as *in silico* simulation of biotech experiments. It is recognized that "wet-lab" experiments cannot be totally replaced with *in silico* simulations. However, if the principle is applied wherever feasible, and especially where toxic or environmentally harmful chemicals are used, it can have a significant positive impact on the environment. The virtual laboratory are developed in Adobe Flash, to ensure that it can be used directly in any Internet browser without the need for installation, and will be made available free of charge online at www.biotechacademy.dk.

Screenshot of the Virtual Greentech Laboratory.